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POZALEKCYJNA WYCHOWAWCZA PRACA JAK JEST WAŻNA SKŁADOWA EDUKACYJNY-WYCHOWAWCZEGO PROCESU W ZAKŁADACH WYKSZTAŁCENIA PODSTAWOWEGO

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W artykule rozpatrzono istotę i efektywność pozalekcyjnej wychowawczej pracy w zakładach wykształcenia podstawowego. Przeanalizowano stopień badania danej problematyki współczesnymi pedagogami-teoretykami i praktykami. Wyjaśniono treść pojęcia «pozalekcyjna praca» we współczesnej ukraińskiej pedagogice. Zarysowano wymogi do klasowego kierownika-głównego organizatora pozalekcyjnej wychowawczej pracy w zakładach wykształcenia podstawowego. Opisano charakterystyczne właściwości, zadania, warunki i formy organizacji pozalekcyjnej działalności. Rozpatrzono ogólne zasady pozalekcyjnej wychowawczej pracy i jej znaczenia w kształtowaniu osobistości młodszych uczniów. Określono rolę pozalekcyjnej wychowawczej pracy w edukacyjno-wychowawczym procesie szkoły. Śledzą współczesne podejścia do pozalekcyjnej wychowawczej działalności. Uzasadniono myśl o tym że, interes uczniów młodszych klas wpływa na efektywność przeprowadzenia pozalekcyjnej wychowawczej pracy.

Kluczowe słowa: wychowawczy proces, zakłady wykształcenia podstawowego, klasowy kierownik, młodszy uczniowie, nauczania, pozalekcyjna praca.

EXTRACURRICULAR EDUCATIONAL WORK AS AN IMPORTANT COMPONENT OF EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN ELEMENTARY EDUCATION ESTABLISHMENTS

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The article deals the essence and efficiency of extracurricular educational work in elementary education establishments. The stage of studying this issue by modern pedagogues-theorists and practitioners is analyzed. The essence of the concepts «extra-curricular activity» in the modern Ukrainian pedagogy is clarified. The requirements for a class teacher, who is the main organizer of the extra-curricular activity on students moral education, are determined. The characteristic features, tasks, conditions and forms of organizing of extracurricular activities are described. The general principles of extracurricular educational work and its importance in the formation of the personality of elementary students are considered. The role of extracurricular educational work in the educational process of the school is determined. Modern approaches to extracurricular activities are traced. The opinion that the interest of elementary students influences the efficiency of extracurricular education work is substantiated.

Keywords: educational process, elementary education establishments, class teacher, elementary students, teaching, extracurricular activities.

ПОЗАКЛАСНА ВИХОВНА РОБОТА ЯК ВАЖЛИВА СКЛАДОВА НАВЧАЛЬНО-ВИХОВНОГО ПРОЦЕСУ В ЗАКЛАДАХ ПОЧАТКОВОЇ ОСВІТИ

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Анотація. У статті розглянуто сутність та ефективність позакласної виховної роботи в закладах початкової освіти. Проаналізовано ступінь дослідження даної проблематики сучасними педагогами-теоретиками та практиками. З'ясовано суть поняття «позакласна робота» у сучасній українській педагогіці. Окреслено вимоги до класного керівника – головного організатора позакласної виховної роботи в закладах початкової освіти. Описано характерні особливості, завдання, умови та форми організації позакласної діяльності. Розглянуто загальні засади позакласної виховної роботи та її значення у формуванні особистості молодших школярів. Визначено роль позакласної виховної роботи в навчально-виховному процесі школи. Простежено сучасні підходи до позакласної виховної діяльності. Обґрунтовано думку про те що, зацікавленість учнів молодших класів впливає на ефективність проведення позакласної виховної роботи.

Ключові слова: виховний процес, заклади початкової освіти, класний керівник, молодші школярі, навчання, позакласна робота.

Formulation of the problem. The main task of the modern school is to ensure the physical, intellectual, social and spiritual development of the student's personality, which is the basis for further education and work. The holistic development of the individual as an ideal of the educational process is formed in an adequate social and pedagogical situation by including the student in the system of relations of the common, that is, perceived by business interpersonal relations, educational-cognitive, subject-transformative, social-communicative, physical-recreational, artistic-aesthetic etc. activities. It is in the activity that creates favorable socio-psychological conditions for the development of creative potential, life activity of students. This should be aimed at both academic and extracurricular educational activities of schoolchildren. This extracurricular activity, which creates an atmosphere of relentlessness, initiative, amateur activity, has a special content, peculiar forms and activities, is an integral part of the whole educational and educational activity of the school. Out-of-school work is a continuation and development of the process carried out in the classroom and is subordinated to the general educational-educational task.

Out-of-school educational activities are aimed at the development of a harmonious personality and is based on the laws of creativity, which involve involving children in real co-creation, intellectual dialogue, harmonization of communication, success, the ability to feel free. Out-of-school activities promote the development of independent thinking, the development of methods of co-creation and intellectual stress.

One of the features of extracurricular work as a pedagogical process is that the child is not afraid to receive an unsatisfactory score. Relying on the uniqueness and uniqueness of each child, the teacher must develop the knowledge gained, transform them into social experience. Due to this, the functional approach to the child, fragmentation in education, intellectual overload are neutralized. The pedagogical process in extracurricular activities contributes to the development of a sense of personal exclusiveness for children in the search and creation of creative ideas. The activities of

the teacher in this process must be organically linked with the activities of children, their mood and the internal state.

The problem of organizing the educational process in extra-curricular time in a modern school is investigated in various aspects: the definition of conceptual foundations for the organization of extracurricular educational work (S. Goncharenko, V. Novoselsky, V. Orzhehovskaya, V. Postavy, L. Khlebnikova, K. Chorna, etc.); psychological aspects of the organization of extra-curricular work in a modern school (I. Bech, M. Borschevsky, A. Grechishkina, O. Krutenky, S. Maksimenko, L. Sokolov, etc.); the problem of content and areas of extra-curricular educational work (T. Demyanyuk, L. Kanishevskaya, A. Kapskaya, B. Kobzar, V. Rybalka, S. Sviridenko, P. Scherban, etc.); teaching and upbringing of students in the process of extracurricular activities (P. Blonsky, V. Kuz, A. Makarenko, S. Rusova, M. Stelmakhovich, V. Sukhomlynsky, K. Ushinsky, S. Shatsky, M. Fitsula, P. Podkassisty, M. Yevtuh, etc.).

The analysis of the pedagogical practice of the modern school has shown that extracurricular education remains a weak link in the activity of the school, it has not acquired a systematic purposeful nature, since the episodicity of educational activities involving individual children, the expansion of the network of subject circles, in which children continue to study, reduce the number of circles by interest lead to the fact that the school life for children ends at the same time as the bell from the last lesson, and then the street takes them. This phenomenon is especially dangerous for the younger generation.

The purpose of the article is to analyze the essence and efficiency of extracurricular educational work in institutions of primary education.

Presenting main material. Out-of-school educational work as an important component of the educational process has undergone a complex and long-term path of formation in educational institutions of Ukraine, respectively, to understand this progress and characteristic tendencies can only from the standpoint of present day, given the current state of its functioning.

Some elements of extracurricular educational work are traced in the works of the teachers of the XIX century, namely - in justifying them the idea of the need for its organization. K. Ushinsky opposed the deprivation of the school's educational functions and tasks and emphasized the expediency of the logical continuation of the student's work in the classroom in the system of influence of reason on the mind, morality on morality, character in character (Sukhomlynskaya, Antonets, Berezovska, 2005, p. 289). The teacher advised to divide the pupils into small circles, in which they must carry out a genuine, actual education (*Nedilko, 1989, p. 189*).

In this context, we are considering the views of M. Pirogov, who noted that "this progress is achieved only by one way - through education." He first drew attention to the importance of developing human dignity in schoolchildren, having established humanity and humanity in education. His most important form in extracurricular work was gymnasium talks, literary evenings, conversations, etc. (*Sukhomlynskaya, Antonets, Berezovsky, 2005, p. 311*).

V. Sukhomlynskyi, who was deeply convinced of the possibilities of extracurricular hours for the comprehensive development of schoolchildren, makes a special contribution to extra-curricular educational work. The essence of extracurricular work was seen by the great teacher in a pedagogically thought-out organization of free time, rational use of leisure students. Necessary conditions recognized the clear

organization of the whole system of extracurricular educational activities, pedagogical support for the system and structure of extracurricular activities, the diversity of forms and methods; the study of the interests of children, the practical orientation of classes, the interest of teachers in this work (*Sukhomlinsky, 1976, pp. 645-647*).

Modern researchers (T. Ilyina, M. Fitsula, S. Smirnov, I. Kotov, E. Shiyarov, and others) define extra-curricular work in school as one of the forms of leisure activities for students, which is organized and conducted in extracurricular time by the children's self-governing bodies for active help and tactical guidance from the pedagogical team, especially class leaders, educators, organizers of extracurricular work.

According to T. Ilyin, the term "extracurricular work" is often determined by the educational work carried out by a class teacher and teacher with students of his school in extra-curricular time (Ilyina, 1984). The definition of M. Fitsula is similar. According to him, extra-curricular work is a diverse educational and educational work aimed at satisfying the interests and requests of children, which is organized by the school's pedagogical team with students during the extra-curricular time (Fitsula, 1997). Y. Konarzhevsky notes that extracurricular educational work is an activity that takes place in a school outside the classroom, but under the direct pedagogical care of a class teacher or other teachers, which consists of such forms that go beyond the classroom and, within the limits of others, Unions of students, including in circles involving pupils of different classes, and educational associations (Basilchuk, 2009).

Scientists S. Smirnov, I. Kotov, E. Shiyarov define extracurricular educational work as an organization as a teacher of various types of activity of pupils in extra-time time, which provide the necessary conditions for the socialization of the child's personality (Basilchuk, 2009).

We share the opinion of specialists who, under extra-curricular educational work at school, understand the purposeful educational work with schoolchildren, which is organized and carried out by teachers, educators, children's self-government bodies at school after lessons, and which is aimed at achieving a single goal: the harmonious development of children and youth, satisfaction of their interests and requests, identification of talented and gifted pupils, creation of conditions for self-education and self-realization of each student (Biletska, 2017, p. 9).

In the context of the problem under investigation, it should be noted that modern Ukrainian legislation defines a class leader as the main organizer of the student collective, which creates conditions for organizing meaningful leisure activities, including organizing and visiting museums, theaters, exhibitions, excursions, events on nature conservation; is responsible for the prevention of neglect, offenses, plans and conducts appropriate educational activities. Organizes educational work taking into account the age and individual psychological characteristics of pupils (pupils), their inclinations, interests, desires, readiness for certain types of activities, as well as the level of formation of the student group, holds thematic class lessons aimed at raising moral values, interest in the question of belonging to the chosen profession (Beletskaya, 2017, pp. 9-10).

Education and education is the only pedagogical process that ensures the formation and versatile development of the student's personality. Experience shows that pedagogical tasks are successfully solved only with the organic combination of educational - educational work during a classroom with a targeted action on the pupil in

extra-curricular time, so extracurricular work is fairly considered as an important part of the school's work.

As you know, extra-curricular educational work is called such activity of the teacher which is directed at the education of the child's personality. The teacher's direction can be either direct or with the help of invitees for this purpose from other institutions, students, senior students. An essential educational element of extracurricular activities - the implementation of socially useful tasks, during which the students develop a sense of responsibility, careful attitude to material values, respect for labor.

It is worth emphasizing another very important aspect of extracurricular work. Wonderful teacher V. Sukhomlynsky wrote: "The logic of the educational process conceals the danger of isolation and isolation, because at school every step emphasizes: to achieve success by your own efforts, do not rely on others because the results of mental work are evaluated individually. To ensure that school life is inspired by the spirit of collectivism, it should not be exhausted by lessons." Out-of-school work brings students together in friendly collectives, connected with common interests and hobbies. It helps to overcome such negative personality traits as closeness, selfishness, undisciplined. Work in collectives, sections - educates students in a spirit of sociability, purposefulness, deep and active interest in science.

According to I. Bekh, when organizing the activities of junior pupils it is necessary to take into account the specifics of this age: mobility, specificity of thinking, greater vulnerability, ability to immitate, the impossibility of long focusing on something for one. Younger students are attracted to cases in which children enter into relationships of cooperation, mutual help, friendship. If collective activity is in the interests of schoolchildren, captures them with their goals, children need to help each other, take care of improving the surrounding life.

As a result of the analysis of modern psychological and pedagogical literature on the organization of extracurricular educational work, one can conclude that the following types of activities are the most optimal for extracurricular educational work with junior pupils: cognitive activity; employment; game activity; artistic and aesthetic activity; sports activities.

The cognitive activity of primary school students in extracurricular activities was the subject of study of many theorists and practitioners (M. Anzhiyevsky, T. Biletska, G. Gavrilichev, I. Demakova, L. Zelenina, I. Kiyancuk, T. Peshkova, I. Podlasy, T. Rabchenyuk, V. Yurchik, etc.).

Cognitive activity of junior pupils should not only satisfy their cognitive interests, but also be designed in such a way that children from simple tasks pass to solving more complex. In elementary classes, cognitive activity in connection with the peculiarities of children's thinking must be under constant pedagogical control and conducted in a certain sequence. Perpetual cognitive activity in comparison with the educational process has more various forms. Children participate in contests, quizzes, listen to conversations, stories about the newest in the world of science and technology, nature, participate in games of a cognitive nature.

According to scientists and practitioners (M. Galaguzov, Y. Grintsay, A. Zhuravlev, L. Kayukov, I. Krasovitsky, A. Solodkov, etc.), the work activity is organized according to the level of preparedness of junior pupils to one or another type work Children organize study guides, make diverse collections, collect natural material

for lessons, remove premises, take care of flowers, and more. In 2-3 grades, the focus is on the social orientation of students' work activities, which contributes to the formation of collective work skills, the education of interest in work. The results of work give children positive emotions, feelings of pleasure, which prompts them to new labor activities. A characteristic feature of the work of junior pupils is that it is accompanied by an acquaintance with the work of adults.

Priority is the value of gaming activity in the lives of junior pupils. Classics of pedagogy and modern educators and psychologists continue to explore the problem of organizing gaming activities. This problem is important in the researches of theorists and innovators, teacher-organizers (L. Aydarova, O. Byk, O. Gazman, T. Dudova, K. Dyakonova, G. Ivochkivna, D. Koishch, E. Kuteyev, C. Lybid, L. Onysyuk, S. Pirog, E. Pristup, M. Solodka, etc.).

Game activity of junior pupils acts as a special form of collective activity and as an element, an important component of all other activities. In the games of children, the world of adults is reflected, because the game younger students know the surrounding reality. The game activity of junior schoolchildren is multifaceted. There are various classification games, among them the most common are games mobile, sports, didactic, developmental, etc. (*Kazanshi, 2014, pp. 62-64*).

Extracurricular activities to a greater extent than a lesson and elective, adapted for the upbringing of certain classes of personality in junior pupils. Part-time classes are non-lesson forms of organization, methods and content. For such work, the teacher must be armed with relevant knowledge. Out-of-school educational work needs to be planned: perspective for the school year and more for half and a quarter. The need for this is determined not only by the association of extracurricular activities with curricula, but also in order to avoid overloading students with extra-curricular activities. Plans for extracurricular work, both in individual subjects and in schools as a whole, are discussed with students' assets, approved by the school principal and then transferred to the entire school in special charts, posters, announcements. Moreover, informing students about certain measures of a mass character is necessary in advance (*Volkova, 2003, pp. 176*).

It should be emphasized that there can be no successful extracurricular educational work without beginning it at the lessons. The principle of the unity of labor and extra-curricular work - the most important principle of the organization of the educational process. It is at the lessons that the teacher sets questions to the students, which should stimulate their curiosity, give the first impulses to reading additional literature on the subject, cause the desire to do with their own hands what is said in the textbook and in the books read. The path to organizing mass and group extra-curricular work lies in the compilation and reading of small additional messages by students at lessons, conducting initially episodic, and then more systematic mass events. Engaging in intensive extra-curricular work is thus from a lesson to mass work. Then, from the total number of students involved in mass work, an active participant is formed - the participants of the circles work and individual students, especially assist the teacher in organizing mass educational work. So the atmosphere of enthusiasm of the subject is gradually created in school, the involvement of everyone in the affairs of the whole team and a coherent system of extra-curricular work arises, in which each element does not exist separately, not in parallel with the other, but in close relationship with them and with the work work.

All extra-curricular work in school is based on the principle of voluntariness. Therefore, especially at first, it is important to find incentives that could be of interest to the students before they get deeper into the subject in the order of passing the school curriculum. Such stimulus may be elements of curiosity, external effectiveness of various demonstrations, elements of the game and theatricalization. Of course, boredom is not a place and a lesson, but extracurricular activities provide exceptionally great opportunities for exciting students' interest, to enter elements of curiosity in extra-curricular classes. They, however, should not be an end in themselves, but should obey the general task of learning.

Extracurricular educational work not only targets the education, but also mastering the subject, and solves the tasks of the curriculum. In the education of volitional qualities, discipline, and healthy situation in the team, it is important to have a proper understanding of the principle of voluntary participation of schoolchildren in extracurricular work whose goal is education. This question does not become a regular type of course, but for extra-curricular work, it seems very significant, which was noticed by many organizers of extra-curricular educational work. This principle means that students of their choices and desires take on one or another work, but do it necessarily. It is this understanding of voluntarism that helps educate a sense of responsibility, a conscious attitude towards oneself, voluntarily assumed responsibilities. Assists in the implementation of this principle of involving a team of younger students in the organizational autonomy and amateur activities. It is useful to get the students to evaluate their work.

The most important place in the system of extracurricular educational work is the implementation of tasks that have a socially useful orientation. One should strive to ensure that all types of activities of individual work of junior pupils during performance, one way or another, could be used in the work of the team in the goal: not just to read a popular book on an issue that is interesting, but also to tell about read comrades in the classroom, interest them in these or other issues. Not just performing an experiment, but also showing it at a lesson, explaining the nature of the observed phenomena, and making sure that the experiment is convenient for demonstration in the audience. The possibilities of the student team, as the practice of many teachers shows, is extremely high, and the students' work can seriously help in expanding the theoretical basis. Without neglecting this, the aspect of the work of students should also take into account the enormous educational effect of work, because nothing contributes to the education of self-esteem, the development of labor skills, careful attitude to material values, as an active, creative work with a specific socially useful purpose.

Conclusions.

So, under extra-curricular work at school, we understand the purposeful educational work with schoolchildren, organized and implemented by teachers, educators, children's self-government bodies at school after classes. It is aimed at achieving a single didactic-educational goal - harmonious development of students, satisfaction of their interests and requests, identification of talented and gifted pupils, as well as creating conditions for self-education, self-education and self-realization of each student.

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